

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DSANE****FIRST NAME: ATO DEAR****PROGRAM CODE: DCCTh****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Quotation Marks (EUCLID 2019, 6-7)
4. Rules of Thumb (EUCLID 2019, 14)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
6. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
7. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)

A COMPREHENSIVE GUIDE TO WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

The focus of the ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack period one revised by Cleenewerck and Gulma (2019) is to provide a guideline for writing academic papers. The course pack which is divided into nine chapters gives a study progression of key elements that must be considered in academic writing.

The first chapter provides a road map on things to consider when writing an academic paper. The subsequent chapters appear to expatiate on the core rules that must serve for academic writing.

Chapter one provided the necessary building blocks which must be considered during academic writing from how to conceptualize a research topic (University of Toronto Research center 1999) thorough to editing and utilizing the required referencing techniques (EUCLID 2019, 1-4).

Some of the aspects the subsequent chapters touched on, was what plagiarism is and how it occurs. Another was on how to apply the Chicago (Turabian) referencing style guide in academic writing. In order to prevent common mistakes that occur in academic writing, chapter seven was dedicated to providing and discussing corrections to be sampled corrected papers. Finally, the course pack ends with a list of common Latin expressions and abbreviations used. It further spells out the need to use their English equivalents in academic writing to avoid content misinterpretation by readers (EUCLID 2019). The course pack provides a comprehensive guide for academic writing.

2) REACTION TO THE COURSE PACK

a) Essay Writing

A good essay seeks to persuade its readers with substantiated facts (EUCLID 2019, 1). Substantiated facts are not generated by merely quoting authoritative sources. It starts right from the point where the idea for the study is conceived through to the point where the work is edited and readied for final submission. Minor details such as allotting adequate time could determine whether an academic essay will be successful or not (ibid.).

In the field of Engineering, I have found that what sets apart the best engineer from the ordinary one, is visualizing and drawing out a plan before setting the plan into motion. In the same way, a successfully written research paper is not based on trial and error. It requires developing an essay plan complete with timelines which may evolve in the course of the study (ibid.).

Brainstorming and researching is key as that forms the basis of the research. Subsequently, a summary must be made of all vital research as this serves as the basis of an academic paper (Emmerson 2005).

In reading the first chapter, I found the references especially useful as in my further readings I discovered an effective technique for writing academic papers while under time constraint. This technique involved listing brainstormed ideas, making a basic outline from the brainstormed ideas, making a rough draft, and finally, proofreading the research paper (Oshima and Hogue 1999, 257). This technique will be useful to students like myself who have to combine the demands of work, family and life with academic studies.

Reading through this chapter, I wished I had been equipped with such a guide during my postgraduate studies and I believe it is an essential guide for academic writing.

b) Plagiarism

During my post graduate education, we were made to understand that plagiarism in academic writing is equivalent to theft under criminal law (Green 2002). In effect,

plagiarism is an ethical offense in academia and must be avoided (Searle 2015). When understood, it is easy to prevent, and I appreciated the fact that the course pack provided a comprehensive guide to aid in avoiding plagiarism.

As a medical engineer, I deal with documents of a sensitive nature and citing verbatim in official communications is encouraged. I find that the rules for long quotations in academic writing differ from that of my work setting. For instance, in academic writing, it is advised to limit quotations as an excess of it gives the impression that the research belongs to another (EUCLID 2019, 7). I appreciate the comprehensive nature of the chapter on plagiarism as it not only serves as a guide to students but also a warning to potential plagiarist (Standler 2012, 76-77).

c) Rules of Thumb to Consider in Academic Writing

When I was in basic school, the general style of writing was to state the thesis in the concluding paragraph. However, as I progressed academically, I was taught that it is essential to state the thesis in the opening paragraph so as to grab the reader's attention. This was emphasized in this course pack as it was advised to state the thesis of the academic paper in the introductory paragraph (EUCLID 2019, 14).

As stated by EUCLID (2019, 16) investing time into your writing now will aid in producing an impeccably written research paper. Investing time by ensuring the rules of thumb provided in the course pack such as that governing plagiarism, discussing your thesis topic seriously, and writing clearly is a good investment of an academic writer's time that will provide significant results in research writing. It is therefore not surprising that these rules of thumb saw me paying extra attention to my potential errors while writing this research report.

d) Basic Differences and Influences of British and American English

Having been mainly trained academically under British English, I find it easier in most instances to identify the differences that exist between British and American English. Nevertheless, following the conventions of a specific style during the writing of an academic paper may be challenging. The advent of popular culture has brought on a blend in American and British English. The conscious effort taken in this course pack to spell out the differences that exist between the two tells me that effort has to be put into writing in order to keep the language consistent with one style of English. When in doubt, it is essential to have a dictionary at hand.

Though keeping to a strict language usage may be challenging, it prevents ambiguity (EUCLID 2019, 27). Again, the distinction between the two teaches that consistency is key when writing an academic paper.

e) Latin Expressions and Abbreviations

Latin is generally considered archaic nonetheless, some people believe the use of Latin makes their writing look more scholarly. The use of Latin in academic text however goes against its basic object as it hinders communication with the reader. The exception, however, is that some Latin abbreviations can be included within bibliographies and footnotes of formal text (EUCLID 2019, 56).

The use of plain and simple language has been emphasized in this course pack and it is reemphasized in the last chapter of the course pack (ibid.). In light of this, a comprehensive list of Latin expressions and abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61) have been included. Though these expressions and abbreviations can be used in the informal context, the use of Latin expressions in place of plain English is discouraged as it can create misunderstanding.

3) CONCLUSION

I enjoyed reading this course pack, however, I found that it left me more critical of my writing style even though I consider myself a fairly good writer. For instance, writing in the first-person singular has never been my style of writing. I have had to reorient myself that the first-person singular is appropriate in formal writing. Having to adapt it in this report was quite the experience and will continue to adapt it going forward.

The fundamentals laid down in ACA-401D has prepared me for the academic journey ahead. Though a learning curve, the course pack will serve as a guide to eliminating errors in my academic writing. In all I considered this pack to be very comprehensive and would recommend it as a guide for academic writing.

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